

The Effectiveness of Employee Wellness Programmes and Civil Service Productivity in Nigeria: A Content Analysis

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Abstract:

This study studied the effectiveness of employee wellness programmes in the Nigerian civil service and their impact on productivity. The research adopted a content analysis approach to systematically analyze and interpret diverse forms of communication related to this topic. The study is grounded in the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model, which emphasizes the interaction between job demands and resources and their influence on employee well-being and performance. The analysis includes a review of empirical studies conducted in Nigeria, examining the barriers, incentives, and outcomes associated with employee wellness programmes. The findings suggested that these programmes can positively affect employee physical and mental health, work-life balance, and overall productivity. However, challenges such as limited time availability and prevailing attitudes towards mental health need to be addressed for effective implementation. The study concludes with recommendations for organizations to enhance their wellness programmes and promote a healthier and more productive workforce in the Nigerian civil service.

Keywords: Employee Wellness Programmes, Civil Service, Productivity, Employee, Employer

Introduction

In recent times, employee wellness programmes have garnered substantial recognition for their role in fostering a robust and efficient workforce. This heightened acknowledgment stems from the realization of their significance in promoting overall well-being and productivity among employees. These programs include various initiatives aimed at improving employees' overall well-being, encompassing physical, mental, and emotional health. Several studies, such as Burton et al., (2017) have consistently demonstrated the positive impact of wellness programs on different aspects of employees' lives. For instance, participation in such programs has been linked to higher

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job satisfaction levels as individuals engage in activities that enhance their well-being, leading to a greater sense of fulfillment at work. Additionally, Ganu et al., (2017) highlighted the substantial benefits of wellness programs on productivity and reduced absenteeism rates. By addressing physical and mental health, these programs assist employees in developing healthier lifestyles, managing stress, and enhancing overall resilience. When considering the Nigerian Civil Service, its origins can be traced back to the organizations established during British colonial times. After gaining full independence in 1960, Nigeria adopted a constitution providing for self-government and a parliamentary system (Nwanolue and Iwuoha, 2012). The term "civil" is derived from the Latin word "civilis," meaning "relating to a citizen," and the old French word "civil," which means "relating to law." Conversely, "service" originates from the old French word "servise," meaning "aids." Throughout its history, the Nigerian Civil Service has undergone numerous reforms and restructuring efforts (Nwanolue and Iwuoha, 2012). Various commissions and panels, such as the Dotun Commission, Adebo Commission, and Udoji Commission, have conducted studies on the Civil Service and made recommendations for improvements. The adoption of a constitution inspired by the United States in 1979 brought significant changes, while the 1988 Civil Service Reorganization Decree, enacted by General Ibrahim Babangida, had a profound impact on its structure and efficiency. Despite these reform attempts, the Civil Service is still perceived as stagnant and inefficient. Previous efforts to improve its functioning have yielded limited results. These reforms included implementing term limits for permanent secretaries and directors, limiting their tenure to a maximum of eight years. President Umaru Yar'Adua approved the reform, which led to a significant retirement of senior officials, particularly from the North.

The Nigerian Civil Service holds a significant position in the management and operation of the country, exerting essential influence over its governance and administration. It is responsible for implementing government policies, delivering public services, and ensuring the smooth operation of various departments and agencies. This makes it a fundamental pillar of the Nigerian government (Ijewereme, 2018). As the government's implementing body, the Civil Service translates policies and decisions into tangible actions and programs. Its primary objective is to execute the developmental plans outlined by the government, aiming to bring positive changes and improvements to the lives of Nigerian citizens. By adhering meticulously to directives and guidelines set by policymakers, the Civil Service helps transform vision into reality. A key aspect of its responsibility is providing essential public services across various sectors such as healthcare, education, infrastructure development, agriculture, and finance. Through its dedicated workforce, the Civil Service ensures that public services are accessible, efficient, and of high quality. Its efforts are directed toward enhancing the well-being of the people, promoting socio-economic development, and fostering an environment conducive to progress. Leveraging its expertise in organizational management, human resources, budgeting, and policy analysis, the Civil Service contributes to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of government operations (Ijewereme, 2018). Nevertheless, Civil Service employees, like any other workforce, face several challenges that can significantly impact their well-being and productivity. These difficulties encompass job-related tension, extensive work hours, and an insufficient equilibrium between work and personal life. These factors collectively have adverse effects on employees' overall performance, leading to reduced productivity, increased absenteeism rates, and potential burnout (Osawe, 2015). Work-related stress is a prevalent issue faced by Civil Service employees due to the demanding nature

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of their roles and responsibilities. The pressure to meet deadlines, handle complex tasks, and navigate bureaucratic processes contributes to a high-stress environment.

Chronic stress not only affects employees' mental and emotional well-being but also has physical consequences, such as fatigue, headaches, and compromised immune systems. Long working hours pose another challenge for Civil Service employees, as they frequently encounter heavy workloads and tight deadlines. The need to complete tasks within limited timeframes results in increased work intensity and extended periods of continuous work. Prolonged exposure to work can lead to fatigue and diminished cognitive functioning, ultimately hindering employees' ability to perform at their best. Inadequate work-life balance persists as a significant issue for many Civil Service employees. The demanding nature of their jobs often requires significant time and energy commitment, leaving limited opportunities for personal pursuits, family commitments, and leisure activities. The imbalance between work and personal life can result in dissatisfaction, stress, and strained relationships. Additionally, it can decrease motivation and engagement in the workplace. Failure to address these challenges can have detrimental effects on the well-being and productivity of Civil Service employees. Decreased performance and productivity may arise from reduced concentration, decreased creativity, and diminished job satisfaction. Moreover, increased rates of absenteeism due to illness or mental health issues can impose additional burdens on individual employees and the organization as a whole. Despite the growing popularity of employee wellness programs, it is essential to evaluate their effectiveness within the unique context of the Nigerian Civil Service. This content analysis will examine existing literature, reports, and case studies to assess the impact of wellness programs on the well-being and productivity of Civil Service employees.

Furthermore, the Civil Service frequently encounters sensitive matters and decision-making procedures that can heighten stress levels. Chronic stress not only impacts the mental and emotional welfare of employees but also manifests in physical symptoms such as fatigue, headaches, and compromised immune systems. The long hours of work present an additional challenge for Civil Service personnel, as they often face heavy workloads and tight deadlines. The necessity to complete tasks within limited timeframes results in heightened work intensity and extended periods of uninterrupted work. Prolonged exposure to work can lead to exhaustion and reduced cognitive performance, ultimately impeding employees' optimal functioning. The issue of inadequate work-life balance persists among numerous Civil Service workers. The demanding nature of their roles often demands significant time and energy, leaving minimal opportunities for personal interests, family commitments, and recreational pursuits. The lack of equilibrium between work and personal life can lead to discontentment, tension, and strained interpersonal connections. Moreover, it can undermine one's drive and involvement in the professional setting. Neglecting these issues can have negative repercussions on the welfare and efficiency of Nigerian Civil Service personnel. Reduced performance and productivity may arise from a lack of concentration, diminished creativity, and decreased job fulfillment. Furthermore, heightened rates of absenteeism due to sickness or mental well-being concerns can impose additional burdens on individual employees and the entire organization. Despite the growing popularity of employee well-being initiatives, it is crucial to evaluate their efficacy within the distinctive framework of the Nigerian Civil Service. This content analysis will evaluate existing literature, reports, and case studies to

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gauge the impact of wellness programs on the well-being and productivity of Civil Service personnel.

Conceptual Clarifications

Employee wellness

According to a study by Okereke and Adinma (2020), wellness programmes, also known as workplace wellness programmes, are comprehensive initiatives designed to enhance and support individuals' overall well-being and promote optimal health and fitness. While these programmes are commonly offered in the workplace, they can also be provided directly to enrollees by insurance plans. The main goal of wellness programmes is to encourage employees or plan members to actively participate in activities and behaviors that contribute to improved health outcomes. Muya et al., (2014) argue that wellness programmes go beyond physical exercise, smoking cessation, or weight management, and have the potential to cultivate a comprehensive wellness culture within an organization. This culture includes elements such as employee engagement and the establishment of social networks that promote organizational citizenship, trust, high performance, and overall productivity.

Well-being encompasses various aspects of a person's life and experiences, according to Seligman (2002), a prominent psychologist in the field of positive psychology. It goes beyond the absence of illness or distress and extends to the pursuit of positive emotions, personal fulfillment, and overall life satisfaction. Well-being includes happiness, satisfaction, vitality, optimism, passion, and self-actualization. Happiness represents positive emotions, contentment, and joy in one's life, while satisfaction refers to an overall evaluation of life and the fulfillment of desires and goals. Vitality involves high energy, enthusiasm, and zest for life, while optimism relates to a positive outlook and maintaining hope even in challenging situations.

Civil service

Civil service, as described by Smalskys and Urbanovič (2017), encompasses individuals who hold positions as civil servants and their responsibilities in executing decisions made by politicians. It is a comprehensive framework comprising dedicated civil servants entrusted with various functions in public administration. Civil servants play a crucial role in upholding good governance principles, ensuring effective policy implementation, and facilitating the smooth functioning of public institutions. They are involved in policy development, program implementation, regulatory enforcement, public service delivery, and administrative support. The civil service system embodies principles such as impartiality, professionalism, meritocracy, and accountability. These principles guide the recruitment, selection, and promotion of civil servants based on qualifications and competence, strengthening public trust and confidence in the civil service.

According to Agbodike et al. (2015), the civil service plays a crucial role in the effective functioning of contemporary governance. It consists of career officials appointed based on their qualifications, expertise, and competence in specific areas. The civil service ensures continuity and stability in governance, functioning as the driving force behind government operations. It supports and implements government policies, programs, and initiatives aimed at promoting socio-

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economic progress and improving the overall well-being of society. By serving as the administrative backbone of the government, the civil service enables efficient and effective governance, coordinating and executing various development programs and projects.

The civil service in Nigeria comprises dedicated individuals employed in various ministries or departments, as highlighted by Abba and Anazodo (cited in Anazodo et al., 2012). They are distinct from political appointees and form the core workforce ensuring continuity and stability in governance. Civil servants play crucial roles in implementing policies, providing administrative support, conducting research, managing public resources, and delivering essential services to citizens. Their expertise and institutional knowledge contribute to the effective functioning of government institutions, fostering efficiency, accountability, and professionalism.

Productivity

Productivity refers to the capacity of an economy or organization to maximize output using available resources while maintaining efficiency and equilibrium in the production process (Krugman, 1994). It serves as a fundamental measure of effectiveness, indicating the optimal utilization of labor, capital, technology, and other production factors. A high level of productivity signifies efficient resource allocation, leading to increased profits, economic growth, improved living standards, and an enhanced quality of life. Factors such as technological advancements, innovation, infrastructure, education, skills, management practices, and government policies influence productivity. By enhancing these factors, productivity can be improved, thereby unlocking the full potential of an economy or organization.

Yadav and Marwah (2015) define productivity as a key metric that quantifies production efficiency. It encompasses various factors that impact overall output and effectiveness, evaluating the ability of individuals, teams, or organizations to achieve desired outcomes relative to the resources employed. Productivity considers the efficiency of converting inputs into valuable goods or services and reflects the ability to maximize output while minimizing resource usage. It encompasses aspects such as resource utilization, effectiveness of work processes, adoption of technology, optimization of workflows, and adaptability to market conditions. The concept of productivity holds significant importance across different fields, enabling analysis and prediction of outcomes based on inputs.

Productivity plays a crucial role in economic analysis, influencing both long-term growth and short-term dynamics (Myronenko & Engdahl, 2012). It informs assessments of fiscal sustainability and economic analyses, thereby guiding policy decisions. When productivity rises alongside favorable labor market conditions, immediate monetary policy tightening may not be necessary. Conversely, economic growth without concurrent productivity gains requires caution due to the potential risks of overheating, speculative bubbles, and inflationary pressures.

Study Limitation

The lack of comprehensive studies on employee wellness programmes in the Nigerian civil service is a significant limitation of this study. The researchers attempted to address this limitation by supplementing their findings with information from newspaper publications and reports. While

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these sources can provide valuable insights, they may not have undergone the same rigorous peer-review process as academic journal articles.

Methodology

This study adopted the Content Analysis approach, a well-established and widely used research method that enables researchers to systematically analyze and interpret the content of diverse forms of communication. By employing this approach, researchers can gain valuable insights into the characteristics, themes, and patterns prevalent in the content they examine, thereby facilitating the drawing of meaningful conclusions. Content Analysis involves a rigorous and systematic examination of different types of communication sources, including but not limited to journals, textbooks, documents, videos, newspaper or magazine publications, online content, social media posts, and even historical records. This comprehensive range of sources allows researchers to explore a broad spectrum of information and perspectives related to their research questions or objectives.

Theoretical Underpinning

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model, introduced by Arnold Bakker and Evangelia Demerouti in 2006, holds significant recognition as a theoretical framework within the field of occupational psychology. This model underscores the interplay between job demands and job resources, and their consequential effects on employee well-being and performance. According to the JD-R Model, job demands encompass the physical, psychological, social, and organizational aspects of work that necessitate continuous effort and entail associated costs and strains. Examples of these demands include workload, time pressure, emotional requirements, and role ambiguity, among others. Conversely, job resources pertain to the physical, psychological, social, or organizational facets of work that facilitate the achievement of work objectives, alleviate job demands, and foster personal growth and development. Instances of job resources encompass social support, autonomy, feedback, training opportunities, and employee wellness initiatives. Employee wellness programs are a specific category of job resources that concentrate on improving the physical and mental well-being of employees. These programs typically consist of activities like health screenings, fitness programs, stress management workshops, and access to counseling services. The JD-R Model posits that organizations can mitigate the adverse effects of job demands and promote employee well-being by providing wellness programs to their employees. Such programs equip employees with resources and strategies to cope with job demands, manage stress, enhance overall health, and bolster resilience. It is important to acknowledge that the effectiveness of employee wellness programs may hinge on various factors, including program design, implementation, organizational culture, and individual characteristics. Moreover, while employee wellness initiatives can be valuable resources, they should not be viewed as a standalone solution for addressing job demands.

Empirical Review

Okereke and Adinma (2020) conducted a research study on employee participation in workplace wellness programs at the Federal University of Technology, Owerri. The study aimed to identify the perceived barriers and incentives for engaging in a comprehensive wellness program at the

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university. A cross-sectional descriptive research design was employed, with the selection of 362 participants carried out using stratified sampling methodology. To collect opinions from eligible worksite health promotion participants, a validated web-based questionnaire adapted from the 2009 Porter Novelli Health Styles Questionnaire was employed. The findings indicated that a significant proportion of respondents (71.8%) expressed a high likelihood of using paid time for exercising at work. Personalized diet or exercise counseling was the most preferred program, with 33.0% showing interest in this type of intervention. The main reported barrier to utilizing worksite wellness services was insufficient time during the work day (46.5%), while the desired incentive for using employee wellness services was the availability of programs at convenient times (41.2%).

Ipole and Okpa (2019) conducted a comprehensive examination on the correlation between working conditions and the productivity of employees within the Civil Service of Cross River State, Nigeria, as detailed in their research titled "The Impact of Working Conditions on Employee Productivity in the Civil Service of Cross River State, Nigeria." The primary focus was to examine the connection between the reward system, promotions, and employees' productivity. A descriptive survey design was employed, and a questionnaire was used as the primary data collection tool. The questionnaire was distributed to 912 staff members working in the Cross River State Civil Service. After conducting statistical analysis using the linear regression method, the data gathered demonstrated a noteworthy association between the reward system, promotions, and the overall productivity of employees. These findings suggest that the reward system and opportunities for promotion play a crucial role in influencing the productivity levels of employees in the Civil Service of Cross River State, Nigeria. This study provides valuable insights into the importance of creating a conducive work environment and implementing effective reward systems and promotional opportunities to enhance employee productivity in the public sector. By recognizing and addressing the factors that contribute to improved productivity, organizations and policymakers can work towards fostering a more efficient and motivated workforce in the civil service.

In a research conducted by Oyedele et al., (2019), an examination was carried out to explore the influence of achieving a harmonious work-life balance on the social aspects of individuals working in the border regions of Lagos Metropolitan. Due to rapid population growth and inadequate social infrastructure, many employees have sought housing in nearby border towns, resulting in job stress and work-life conflicts. The research aimed to understand the consequences of work-life imbalance on job satisfaction and well-being. The impact of work-life balance on the social life of workers was examined in this study through a survey and interviews conducted with a sample of 242 respondents. The results indicated a noteworthy correlation between work-life balance and social aspects among the participants. Recommendations included individuals taking an active role, organizations implementing supportive policies and flexible work strategies, and government intervention to improve transportation and incentivize work-life balance.

In a study by Akhigbe in 2021, the focus was on examining the connection between employee well-being and organizational effectiveness within oil and gas firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. In this study, a cross-sectional survey design was utilized, targeting a population of 665 individuals who were employees in 10 different oil and gas companies in the specified region. A sample size

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of 250 participants was chosen through a simple random sampling method, and data were gathered by administering a questionnaire. To analyze the data, the Spearman rank-order correlation was employed. The results demonstrated a significant positive relationship between employee well-being, measured through dimensions such as job satisfaction and work-life balance satisfaction, and organizational factors such as cohesion and productivity. These findings suggest that by improving employee well-being, job satisfaction, and work-life balance, organizations can enhance their overall effectiveness. Based on the study's outcomes, several recommendations were proposed, including prioritizing the implementation of strategies that effectively reward and recognize employees to boost job satisfaction and improve overall effectiveness.

Ganu et al., (2017) conducted a study titled "The Implementation of Workplace Wellness Programme and its Impact on Employee Work Productivity: The Case of Safaricom Company Ltd" to examine the effects of workplace fitness programs on employee job performance. The study utilized a cross-sectional design and involved 150 employees from the telephone communication industry who participated in telephone interviews. The findings indicated that the implementation of fitness programs had a positive impact on work performance and productivity. Physically active employees had a lower sick leave rate, better physical and mental well-being, and fewer medical problems compared to those who did not participate in any exercise program. Implementing employee health and fitness programs in the workplace can contribute to enhanced work performance and productivity, benefiting both employees and employers.

In an article titled "Workplace Wellbeing As a Business Strategy" written by Talabi, O. (2015), the importance of addressing the issue of poor lifestyle and its impact on employee wellbeing in the Nigerian context is highlighted. The article emphasizes the need for implementing wellness programs in the workplace to improve the physical, mental, and emotional health of employees. It discusses the sedentary nature of work for Nigerians, particularly those living in Lagos, and the resulting physical and mental exhaustion. The article also addresses the healthcare expenses and productivity losses associated with an unhealthy lifestyle. Implementing workplace wellness programs is presented as a proactive approach to educate and equip employees with the knowledge and skills to maintain a healthy body and mind despite work pressures. The article concludes by emphasizing the financial, physical, mental, and emotional benefits of taking a preventative approach to healthcare. The author suggests that both employers and employees should actively promote workplace wellness for shared benefits.

Relationship between Employee Wellness Programmes and Civil Service Productivity in Nigeria

The implementation of employee wellness initiatives in Nigeria's civil service can greatly impact productivity when appropriately executed across all government sectors. When efficiently administered, they can produce various advantages that positively influence employee productivity. This analysis comprehensively examines the different programs, advantages, and applications implemented within Nigeria's civil service, with the goal of evaluating their overall effectiveness.

Employee wellness programmes in the Nigerian civil service often encompass activities such as fitness programs, health screenings, and nutritional education. These initiatives seek to foster healthy habits among employees, ultimately leading to enhanced physical health. When employees are in good physical condition, they tend to exhibit increased energy levels, reduced absenteeism, and lower healthcare expenses, all of which contribute to heightened productivity. Regular participation in fitness activities offered through wellness programs encourages employees to engage in physical exercise, which brings about numerous benefits for their overall well-being. Exercise assists in maintaining a healthy weight, reducing the risk of chronic ailments, improving cardiovascular health, and boosting immune function. When employees enjoy good physical health, they are less prone to illness or fatigue, enabling them to carry out their duties efficiently and consistently. Additionally, wellness programs often include health screenings and nutritional education to raise awareness about preventive health measures and encourage healthy eating habits. By addressing these aspects, employees become more mindful of their health and are better equipped to make informed choices concerning their well-being. This can lead to a decrease in health-related absences and increased productivity due to improved physical health overall. However, a comprehensive study conducted by Okereke and Adinma in 2020 strongly emphasized that the main challenge identified by participants was the insufficient time available during the workday. This finding highlights the significant obstacle faced by individuals in allocating time and attention to specific programs or activities. Despite recognizing the importance of such initiatives, employees expressed difficulties in finding sufficient time within their busy schedules, thereby making it challenging to fully engage in these endeavors. Furthermore, the research findings also revealed that the desired incentive for participants was the availability of programmes at convenient times. Participants expressed a strong preference for initiatives that accommodated their existing commitments and allowed them to participate without significant disruptions to their daily routines.

The mental well-being and productivity of individuals are profoundly interconnected. In the context of the Nigerian civil service, initiatives focused on promoting employee wellness assume a crucial role in addressing mental health concerns. These comprehensive programs encompass an array of supportive measures such as stress alleviation strategies, counseling provisions, and mindfulness training, aiming to cater to the diverse mental health requirements of employees. In Nigeria, there is a prevailing issue surrounding the perception and treatment of mental health conditions, which unfortunately extends to civil servants as well (Wada et al., 2021). Regrettably, many Nigerians fail to take their mental health seriously, leading to a detrimental impact on individuals and society as a whole. When the topic of mental health arises, it is all too common for people to associate it with psychiatric patients or individuals considered "mad." This stereotype perpetuates the stigmatization of mental health issues, exacerbating the challenges faced by those in need of support. Moreover, discussing mental health problems openly often elicits suspicion, rejection, and social sanctions for the person initiating the conversation. In Nigerian society, there is a tendency to view mental health concerns as taboo or signs of weakness. Consequently, individuals who dare to express their struggles with mental health face judgment, discrimination, and isolation from their colleagues and friends. This prevailing attitude towards mental health in Nigeria poses significant barriers to seeking and receiving adequate support. This leads to a lack of awareness, understanding, and empathy surrounding mental health conditions, further

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perpetuating the cycle of ignorance and prejudice. According to a newspaper report by Onyeji (2018), mental disorders in Nigeria are commonly associated with a specific image: that of a disheveled and nude individual who appears completely detached from their surroundings. However, it is crucial to understand that this portrayal represents only a fraction of the diverse range of mental disorders known to exist in Nigeria. Although this extreme case can be considered a severe manifestation of the condition, it is important not to generalize all mental disorders based on this stereotypical representation. In Nigeria, individuals with mental health disorders often face stigmatization, neglect, or inadequate understanding, leading to a rise in the prevalence of these conditions. According to the World Health Organization's 2017 World Health Day Data, approximately 7 million Nigerians experience depression, which is one of the most overlooked and misunderstood mental disorders in the country (Onyeji, 2018).

Employee wellness initiatives frequently highlight the significance of achieving a harmonious equilibrium between work and personal life while offering support to enable employees to skillfully navigate their professional and personal commitments. In the Nigerian civil service, where work demands can be demanding and stressful, supporting work-life balance is crucial. However, Akhigbe (2021) examined the relationship between employee well-being and organizational effectiveness in the oil and gas firms located in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings demonstrated a significant positive relationship between employee well-being, measured through dimensions like job satisfaction and work-life balance satisfaction, and organizational factors such as cohesion and productivity. Furthermore, the study conducted by Oyedele and colleagues (2019) examined the influence of achieving a harmonious equilibrium between work and personal life on the social aspects of individuals residing in border towns within the Lagos Metropolitan area. The findings indicated that work-life balance significantly affects workers' social life. When employees feel supported in achieving a healthy work-life balance, they experience less burnout and are better able to focus on their work responsibilities. Wellness programs may offer flexible work arrangements, time management training, or provide access to resources such as child care or elder care support. These initiatives empower employees to fulfill their personal obligations while maintaining their productivity at work.

Conclusion

Employee wellness programmes, when designed and implemented effectively, have the potential to positively impact civil service productivity in Nigeria. These programmes can improve physical and mental well-being, reduce absenteeism, and enhance work-life balance among employees. However, it is important to consider the specific needs and challenges of the Nigerian context, including the prevailing attitudes towards mental health and the demands of the civil service sector. By addressing these factors and implementing comprehensive wellness programmes, organizations in the Nigerian civil service can foster a healthier and more productive workforce, leading to enhanced overall productivity and organizational effectiveness.

Recommendations

Organizations can consider implementing the following recommendations to enhance their employee wellness programmes and productivities:

- i. Government should offer flexitime or remote work options to allow employees to have more control over their schedules and allocate time for wellness activities without disrupting their daily routines.
- ii. Prioritize mental health support by offering counseling services, stress management techniques, and mindfulness training to help employees cope with work-related stress and improve their overall well-being.
- iii. The provision of necessary assistance and resources by the government to employees, aiding them in effectively balancing their personal and professional responsibilities, is imperative. This measure ensures employees can uphold their productivity levels while fulfilling their individual obligations.

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